

Research Paper

Cascade hydroponics enhanced water and nutrients use efficiency in a greenhouse cucumber-melon crop combination

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing the sustainability of horticultural crops in the Mediterranean region is of great importance, with a particular focus on the simultaneous reduction of water and fertiliser consumption and the improvement in crop productivity. In the current study, the efficacy of a cascade soilless system was assessed, which utilised the drainage of a cucumber (donor) cultivation to meet the nutritional and water needs of a melon (receiver) crop, both grown in perlite slabs. Melon crop irrigated with standard nutrient solution, served as control treatment. The cascade system was assessed in terms of water (WUE), nitrogen (NUE), phosphorus (PUE), and potassium (KUE) use efficiency. In addition, the total consumption and the mineral composition of the supplied nutrient solution during cropping were monitored and the N and P emissions to the environment were estimated. The effects of the treatments on plant growth and yield as well as the nutrient absorption of the melon crop, was also examined. The results showed that the WUE of the cascade system demonstrated a 22% increase compared to the cucumber monoculture system. The NUE and PUE increased substantially by 21.7% and 21.8% compared to the monoculture system respectively, while the KUE increased by 9%. Notably, plant growth and yield of the receiver crop were not affected when fertigated with the drainage solution derived from a cucumber crop. Finally, the implementation of the cascade system contributed to a remarkable reduction in N and P leaching into the environment by 70% and 86%, respectively. These results underscore the potential of cascade soilless systems as a sustainable and resource-efficient approach in Mediterranean horticulture.

1. Introduction

The European Union, in the framework of the Green Deal and the Zero Pollution Action Plan, aims to limit N and P emissions to the soil, water, and air. Closed hydroponic systems may be considered as key technique in greenhouses to tackle this challenge, as they provide the opportunity to maximize water and nutrient use efficiency while minimizing the environmental impact of the production system (Katsoulas et al., 2015). However, recycling the nutrient solution within arid and semiarid zones, such as the coastal Mediterranean region, constrains the potential for completely closed systems due to elevated salt concentrations (Na^+ and Cl^- , but also high Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and SO_4^{2-}) (Katsoulas and Voogt, 2013), present in the water used for preparing nutrient solutions (Bar-Yosef, 2008). In order to avoid salt accumulation in the root zone, when the concentration of toxic ions (e.g. Na^+) reaches a maximum threshold level the partial discharge of the drainage solution is necessary (semi-closed systems) (Pardossi et al., 2006; Massa et al., 2020).

However, when relevant discharge regulations are in place, the discharge of the nutrient solution into the environment is allowed for a certain level of Na^+ (e.g. 8 mmol L^{-1} for tomato crop in the Netherlands) (Stanghellini et al., 2005). The nutrient solution discharged from semi-closed and free drainage (open) systems results in water and nutrient waste causing significant environmental pollution (Puccinelli et al., 2023a). As a consequence, the study of different drainage management strategies is necessary for minimising water loss and nutrient leaching into the environment while increasing crop sustainability. When the drainage solution is not reused (open systems) or cannot undergo further recycling (semi-closed systems), instead of being discharged into the environment, the effluents can be collected and reused in a less sensitive to salinity crop (Massa et al., 2020; Puccinelli et al., 2023b) or as input to different production processes such as microalgae production (Richa et al., 2020; Faliagka et al., 2024).

Within a cascade hydroponic system, the drainage nutrient solution from a primary (donor) crop, is used to meet the nutritional needs of a

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secondary (receiver) crop (or even a tertiary crop) that exhibits higher tolerance to salinity. As the drainage solution undergoes successive reuse, it becomes progressively more saline due to the accumulation of the non-absorbed ions. However, the volume of the resulting drainage of a cascade cropping system is significantly lower compared to the drainage volume of a monoculture system as the same solution is reused rather than being discarded after each crop cycle. Therefore, when the drainage solution is eventually discharged due to high salinity levels, it is less harmful to the environment compared to larger volumes of nutrient-rich runoff solutions derived from monoculture systems (Incrocci et al., 2003). These systems have the potential to maximise water use efficiency (WUE) while concurrently reduce nutrient leachate (García-Caparrós et al., 2018a).

Innovative applications of these systems were first developed for open-field crops in California’s San Joaquin Valley about thirty years ago (Grieve and Suarez, 1997; Jacobsen, 2004). In the past two decades, research has increasingly focused on cascade cropping systems in soil-less crops (Incrocci et al., 2003; Muñoz et al., 2012; Elvanidi et al., 2020; García-Caparrós et al., 2021; Puccinelli et al., 2023a). Karatsivou et al., (2023) found that applying raw or diluted drainage from tomato crop to leafy vegetables did not affect leafy vegetables yield. García-Caparrós et al., (2018a) used a blended drainage solution from melons with low EC water for rosemary and cacti production, saving water and nutrients. Cascade systems can also be hybrid soilless-soil systems (Zhang et al., 2006; Muñoz et al., 2012) reducing the environmental impact.

Variability between crops emerges as a major limiting factor in the implementation of a cascade system (Massa et al., 2020). The drainage solution from the primary crop should meet the secondary crop’s nutritional and irrigation needs. Adapting facilities and equipment for the main crop can complicate secondary crop cultivation. Hydroponic co-cultivation of species within the same genus may lead to phenomena such as the spreading of root pathogens and autotoxicity (Yu and Matsui, 1993; Singh et al., 1999; Hosseinzadeh et al., 2017), while the co-cultivation between different species may result in allelopathy (Kim et al., 2005; Ding et al., 2019). Low-input secondary crops, typically produce lower yields per unit area, which can negatively affect the producer’s income (Massa et al., 2020). Therefore, crop selection, system design, and irrigation strategy are crucial for successful implementation of a cascade system. To date, there has been a lack of studies focusing on the performance of these systems in terms of water productivity, pollution reduction, and the optimal crop species combination to maximise production per unit area.

Considering the above, the objective of this study was to evaluate the performance of a cascade soilless (on perlite) cultivation system in terms of (a) water (WUE), nitrogen (NUE), phosphorus (PUE), and potassium use efficiency (KUE) and (b) leaching reduction, wherein cucumber plants serve as a primary crop, and their drainages were used for the subsequent irrigation of melon plants as a secondary crop. The selection of melon crop as a secondary crop stems from its higher salinity tolerance compared to the cucumber crop, coupled with similar cultivation techniques and nutrient needs (Bar-Yosef, 2008).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Site description

This work was conducted at the pilot greenhouse park of the Laboratory of Agricultural Constructions and Environmental Control, Department of Agriculture, Crop Production and Rural Environment, University of Thessaly, located in the area of Velestino, Central Greece (39° 22’, 22° 44’, 85 m). The installation of the cascade system was carried out in two different greenhouses (Fig. 1). The primary crop was cultivated into two adjacent compartments of a gothic-arch type greenhouse, while the secondary crop was cultivated in a single-span arched roof greenhouse. Both greenhouses were oriented in a north-south direction. The climate conditions inside and outside the

Fig. 1. (a) Primary crop cultivation, (b) secondary crop cultivation (c) the cucumber monoculture and the cascade and melon monoculture system setup, and (d) floor plan and the interconnection between primary and secondary crop greenhouses.

secondary crop greenhouse are presented in Table S1 of supplementary material.

2.1.1. Primary crop

The primary cucumber crop (*Cucumis sativus* cv. Columbia) was cultivated in two compartments, each having a total ground area of 240 m² (25 m long, 9.6 m wide, 7.4 m in ridge height). The roof of the greenhouse consisted of UV-resistant polyethylene film, and the side walls were sheathed with polycarbonate sheets. Within each compartment, there were six hydroponic channels, each spanning a length of 19 m. The environmental conditions in the greenhouse were controlled and recorded every five minutes using a climate control computer (SERCOM, Automation SL, Lisse, the Netherlands). The roof of each compartment was equipped with a continuous vent for ventilation while the natural ventilation, was activated when the air temperature exceeded 24 °C. The cooling system consisted of a wet pad and a fan and was activated when the internal air temperature reached values higher than 26 °C. The heating system incorporated an oil boiler integrated with metallic tubes “rail system” was activated when the inner air temperature was below 14 °C. For shading and energy conservation, a thermal-shading screen was installed inside the greenhouse, at the height of eaves (5 m). The thermal-shading screen transparency was 0.50 and was activated when solar radiation outside the greenhouse exceeded 750 W m⁻².

The water and nutrient supply was carried out via an automatic programmable logic controller (PLC) (Argos Electronics, Athens, Greece). The optimum nutrient concentration to form the nutrient solution for the vegetative and fruit stage of the cucumber crop (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009), was prepared within the hydroponic head (500 L). An injection system was adapted on the hydroponic head to mix the stock solutions with groundwater accompanied with pH-EC sensors. Following the attainment of the targeted pH and EC values, the nutrient solution was subsequently transferred to the irrigation tank. Two irrigation tanks (500 L) corresponded to each compartment, whereas the nutrient solution from each of these tanks ended up in the respective drainage tank (300 L). Water pressure meters were installed at the irrigation and drainage tanks to monitor the volumes of irrigation and drainage from the cultivation. These sensors were connected into the PLC system, allowing continuously monitoring and recording.

2.1.2. Secondary crop

The secondary crop (*Cucumis melo* cv. Masada) was cultivated into a single-span arched roof greenhouse, encompassing a total ground area of 160 m² and a cultivated area of 80 m² covered by a polyethylene film. Inside the greenhouse, eight hydroponic channels were installed, each measuring 12.5 m in length. The greenhouse was equipped with a continuous vent, a fog system and an oil boiler linked both with plastic tubes and a fan heater. The climate was automatically controlled with a climate computer (Argos Electronics, Athens, Greece) with the data collected being transmitted seamlessly to a central database. The recording of the climate data in the database was carried out with a frequency of 15 minutes. The heating system was triggered when the day and night temperature dropped below 18 °C and 16 °C, respectively. Conversely, the ventilation system was activated when the inside air temperature exceeded 22 °C and the fog system when temperature surpassed 25 °C. Moreover, in order to reduce the incoming solar radiation during the summer months, a whitening in the greenhouse roof was implemented on June 12, 2023.

A fertigation head (Argos Electronics, Athens, Greece) was used to automatically prepare the nutrient solution for the secondary crop. The preparation process of the nutrient solution was similar to the primary crop. Prior to transferring the prepared irrigation solution from the fertigation head to the irrigation tank, the volume of the nutrient solution was recorded using a pressure meter, with the data integrated into a centralised database. The collected drainage solution, before its discharge, was circulated back to the fertigation head through a pump. This process was carried out in order to record, the volume of the

drainage nutrient solution, for accurate record-keeping and comprehensive analysis.

2.2. Plant material and experimental setup

The primary crop was transplanted on March 15, 2023 (20 days after sowing) and terminated on July 22, 2023, while the secondary crop was transplanted on April 10, 2023 and terminated along with the primary crop. The seedlings of both crops were provided in 7.5 cm × 7.5 cm rockwool cubes (Grodan International, Netherlands) at the stage where they had formed 2 leaves and transplanted on perlite bags (Hydroperl, granules of 0.5 - 2.5 mm in diameter, total porosity of 95%, Nordiaagro, Athens, Greece). In total, 228 cucumber plants were used in each compartment, resulting in a planting density of 1.08 plants per m², whereas in the case of the secondary crop, a total of 208 melon seedlings were placed in the eight hydroponic channels with a plant density of 2.2 plants per m².

In the case of the melon crop, the two hydroponic channels located at the left and right edge of the greenhouse were utilised solely to exclude border effects. Two different fertigation treatments were applied in the remaining six experimental channels consisting of three replications each. Particularly, in the first treatment (control), melon plants were fertigated with a standard hydroponic nutrient solution for the melon crop (Sonneveld and Straver, 1988) (Table S2). The concentration of the nutrients in the irrigation and drainage nutrient solution of the cucumber crop are presented in Table 1. In the second treatment (cascade), the crop was fertigated with the drainage derived from the primary crop following pH correction. The target pH value of both treatments was set at 5.8, while the pH adjustment was performed through the addition of nitric acid.

Fig. 1 illustrates the systems evaluated in this study. In the cascade treatment, a melon crop (melon cascade) was irrigated with the drainage solution from the cucumber crop (primary crop), after pH adjustment. To compare its effectiveness, monoculture systems for both cucumber and melon (melon control) were also examined as separate, monoculture systems. In this scenario, the nutrient solution of the monoculture systems represented a new input, whereas in the cascade system, the irrigation solution was a recycled input. Additionally, an alternative system was tested, referred to as the single system. In this system, both cucumber and melon control were considered to be cultivated together in an optimal area ratio, but the melons were irrigated with fresh

Table 1

Mean values of the irrigation nutrient solution analysis (± S.E.) of the primary crop, and the melon control treatment and the melon cascade treatment.

	Cucumber		Melon vegetative stage		Melon fruit stage	
	Irrigation	Drainage	Control	Cascade	Control	Cascade
pH	5.88 ± 0.09	6.38 ± 0.05	6.09 ± 0.01 ^a	5.75 ± 0.02 ^b	6.20 ± 0.01 ^a	6.26 ± 0.06 ^a
EC	2.21 ± 0.02	2.51 ± 0.03	2.64 ± 0.03 ^b	2.88 ± 0.04 ^a	2.36 ± 0.00 ^a	2.50 ± 0.10 ^a
NO₃⁻	11.07 ± 0.07	10.91 ± 0.04	11.20 ± 0.09 ^b	11.85 ± 0.06 ^a	9.47 ± 0.04 ^b	10.04 ± 0.05 ^a
NH₄⁺	1.29 ± 0.10	0.24 ± 0.04	1.18 ± 0.01 ^a	0.45 ± 0.02 ^b	0.80 ± 0.01 ^a	0.10 ± 0.00 ^b
PO₄³⁻	1.11 ± 0.05	0.7 ± 0.05	1.56 ± 0.09 ^a	1.05 ± 0.01 ^b	1.13 ± 0.02 ^a	0.74 ± 0.01 ^b
K⁺	8.67 ± 0.53	6.36 ± 0.28	7.43 ± 0.07 ^b	9.51 ± 0.34 ^a	7.53 ± 0.08 ^a	5.98 ± 0.02 ^b
Ca²⁺	3.12 ± 0.21	4.05 ± 0.32	4.58 ± 0.22 ^a	4.63 ± 0.15 ^a	3.31 ± 0.11 ^b	4.21 ± 0.01 ^a
Na⁺	1.78 ± 0.02	2.75 ± 0.22	1.86 ± 0.05 ^b	3.20 ± 0.17 ^a	1.71 ± 0.01 ^b	2.76 ± 0.03 ^a

^aEC in dS m⁻¹; concentration of all macronutrients (NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, PO₄³⁻, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺) in mmol L⁻¹. Lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences among the melon control and melon cascade treatments for either the vegetative or fruit growth stage.

nutrient solution, unlike the recycled solution in the cascade system. The evaluation focused on the ratio of the cultivated areas of the primary and secondary crops.

2.3. Cascade system setup

The process of drainage reusing into the cascade crop was controlled automatically between the two different greenhouses. Every two days, the accumulated drainage from the primary crop was transferred through a plastic tube into a collection tank (400 L) placed inside the secondary crop greenhouse. Each time the fertigation head was activated to prepare the melon cascade treatment solution, the solution was drawn from the collection tank. After pH adjustments, the nutrient solution followed the same procedure as that of the control treatment. The irrigation frequency was regulated by the PLC timer and primarily based on weather conditions (solar radiation and temperature). For both crops, on cloudy days the irrigation system was activated from 3 to 5 times per day, whereas during days with high solar radiation the frequency increased by up to 10 irrigation events per day. The average irrigation dosage per irrigation event for both crops was about 0.5 L m^{-2} . To prevent the accumulation of salts in the root zone, the rate of nutrient solution application was adjusted to cover the plant consumption plus 25–35% surplus for drainage. The quantity of water added along with the pH and EC values is reported in the results.

2.4. Measurements and analyses

Air temperature (T, in °C) and relative humidity (RH, in %) of the secondary crop greenhouse, were measured using a temperature-humidity sensor in both greenhouses, placed 1.8 m above ground level. Global radiation (W m^{-2}) was recorded using a solar pyranometer.

The assessment of both plant height and leaf count was conducted for a subset of 15 marked plants within the secondary crop for each treatment at 10-day intervals, spanning the experimental period up to day 50 when the growing point of the main stem top cut. Plant height was estimated by measuring the distance between the point of contact of the plant with the substrate and the plant top.

During the cultivation period, four destructive measurements were carried out to estimate the fresh and dry matter of the crops. The first destructive measurement was performed during the day of transplanting the secondary crop (DAT 0). The subsequent measurements were conducted with a 30-day interval. On each destructive measurement, the aboveground part of 5 pre-determined plants per treatment was collected and the samples were separated into leaves, stems, and fruits. The fresh weight of all fruits from all fruits, as well as leaves and stems, was summed to achieve the total fresh weight production. To determine the dry weight of the plants, the samples were placed in a drying oven at 70°C for 72 h.

Plant tissue analysis of the leaves, stems, and fruits, was conducted for every destructive measurement. To determine the effect of the recycled nutrient solution on the concentration of the main macronutrients, N, P, K, Ca, and Na analysis was performed in the leaf tissue. The determination of non-volatile macronutrients (K, Ca, Na, P) in the plant tissue, was carried out by high-temperature dry ashing of the organic matter, and 6% hydrochloric acid (HCL) dissolution. Ca, Na, and K concentrations were estimated using a flame photometer (PFP7, Jenway Technology Company, Hong Kong, China), while the amount of P was measured by ammonium vanadate-molybdate/ascorbic acid blue method, using a spectrophotometer (UV 1900, SHIMADZU, Kioto, Japan) in 882 nm. Due to high sensitivity of the spectrophotometer the sample was diluted 100 times. The estimation of the total nitrogen in the plant tissue was carried out via the Kjeldhal method using a Raypa DNP 2000 distiller (RAYPA, Barcelona, Spain). 0.2 gr of dried tissue was added with 20 mL sulphuric acid and 2 tablets of copper sulphate catalysts in a digestion flask. After digestion, the solution was neutralized with 80 mL sodium hydroxide. The titration was carried out using

methyl red.

The plant yield was obtained from 15 marked plants of each treatment. The first fruit harvest commenced approximately two months after transplantation (DAT 70) and continued in a weekly basis until the end of the cultivation period. In total, six harvests were conducted during the experimental period. The fresh weight of each fruit was individually recorded, while no fruits were deemed unmarketable for both treatments. In each harvest, the number of harvested fruits of the marked plants was also recorded. The plant yield and the number of fruits produced per m^2 were estimated based on the plant density.

2.5. Nutrient solution composition parameters

To evaluate nutrient solution composition parameters, sampling of irrigation and drainage solution of both cultivations was carried out once a week. The samples of the irrigation solution were collected directly from the irrigation drippers used to irrigate the crop. Simultaneously, samples of drainage water were collected from the drainage pipes positioned at the termination point of each experimental channel. Measurements of EC and pH values were performed using a portable pH-EC sensor (Combo pH-EC-TDS-Temp, 98,130 Hanna Instruments, Woonsocket, RI, USA). To determine the concentrations of K, Ca, and Na, the samples were analysed using a Flame Photometer. Nitrates were quantified using a Nitro::lyser sensor (s::can GmbH, Vienna, Austria), while ammonium and phosphates were assessed using a spectrophotometer (HACH DR3900, Loveland, CO, USA).

2.6. Calculations

The total volume of irrigation (VIR) and drainage (VDR) applied and drained from each crop (L m^{-2}) was calculated as the sum of water added or drained during each irrigation event throughout the entire growing season and divided by the total cultivated area. As shown in Eq. 1, the drainages from the primary crop and both the irrigation and drainage solution of the secondary crop were considered to determine the total volume of the drainage leached into the environment using the cascade system (VDR_{CS} , L m^{-2}). Specifically, the product of the total drainage volume from the primary crop (VDR_{PC} , L m^{-2}) and the total drainage volume of the secondary crop (VDR_{SC} , L m^{-2}) was divided by the total volume of irrigation solution supplied to the secondary crop (VIR_{SC} , L m^{-2}) throughout the entire cultivation season.

$$\text{VDR}_{CS} = \frac{\text{VDR}_{PC}}{\text{VIR}_{SC}} * \text{VDR}_{SC} \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, the nitrogen and phosphorus leaching (LC_x , g m^{-2}) of the primary and secondary crop was calculated using Eq. 2 and represents the total amount of each nutrient leached into the environment.

$$\text{LC}_x = \text{CDR}_x * \text{VDR}_x \quad (2)$$

where, CDR_x is the concentration of each nutrient in the drainage solution (mg L^{-1}) and VDR_x is the total drainage volume of the cultivation period (L m^{-2}). The calculation of nutrient leaching in the cascade system (g m^{-2}) was determined using the Eq. 3.

$$\text{LC}_x = \text{CDR}_x * \frac{\text{VDR}_{PC}}{\text{VIR}_{SC}} \left(1 + \frac{\text{VDR}_{SC}}{\text{VIR}_{SC}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The water use efficiency (WUE , kg m^{-3}) of the primary and secondary crop was determined as the ratio of the total fruit yield (Y , kg m^{-2}) to the total volume of irrigation nutrient solution (VIR , $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-2}$) of each crop throughout the entire cultivation period. Similarly, the nitrogen and phosphorus use efficiency (NUE and PUE , kg^{-1}) were the result of the division of the total fruit yield (Y , kg) to the total amount of N (kg) and P (kg) supplied to the crop. Furthermore, the WUE was estimated for the cascade (Eq. 4) and the monoculture system (Eq. 5).

Following a similar notion, NUE and PUE were also estimated for both the cascade and a monoculture cropping system.

$$WUE_{CS} = \frac{\left(Y_{PC} + \frac{VDR_{PC}}{VIR_{SC}} * Y_{SC} \right)}{VIR_{PC}} \quad (4)$$

$$WUE_{SS} = \frac{\left(Y_{PC} + \frac{VDR_{PC}}{VIR_{SC}} * Y_{SC} \right)}{\left(VIR_{PC} + \frac{VDR_{PC}}{VIR_{SC}} * VIR_{SC} \right)} \quad (5)$$

For the calculation of WUE of the monoculture system, the irrigated nutrient solution of the secondary crop was included in Eq. 5. The WUE of the monoculture and the cascade system was compared in order to assess the application of such a system per unit area.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Comparison of means was performed by applying one-way ANOVA at a confidence level of 95% ($p \leq 0.05$) using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences, IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Additionally, multiple comparison of means was performed using the LSD test at the 5% level of significance. In the case the data did not follow a normal distribution, a non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis test ($p \leq 0.05$) was applied. The mean values and standard errors (\pm SE) of the measured parameters are also reported.

3. Results

3.1. Nutrient solution composition and consumption

Values of pH and EC are pivotal in examining the nutrient solution (NS) composition. As expected, the pH values of the supplied nutrient solution to the melon crops (Fig. 2a) followed a similar trend line for both treatments, due to pH adjusting (the relevant values observed in the primary crop are also presented for comparison). The average irrigation pH values during the cultivation period for the melon control and the cascade treatment were 6.1 and 6.0, respectively. Similarly, the pH values of drainage nutrient solution (Fig. 2b) did not differ between the secondary crop treatments over the cultivation period as the average

Fig. 2. Evolution of the mean values of pH and EC (ds m^{-1}) (\pm S.E.) of the irrigation (a, c) and drainage (b, d) nutrient solutions of the melon control and the melon cascade treatment. The relevant values observed in the primary cucumber crop are also presented for comparison reasons.

values were 6.30 and 6.43 for the melon control and the cascade treatment, respectively.

The EC variation in the irrigation nutrient solution of the melon control and cascade treatments is presented in Fig. 2c. In general, the EC of the irrigation solution of the secondary crop, presented similar values between treatments, especially during the fruit developmental stage, highlighting the EC similarity between a standard nutrient solution for melon crops and the cascade one resulting from cucumber drainages.

The EC values of the drainage solution of the secondary crop (Fig. 2d), showed a variation during the cultivation period. At the vegetative stage (after DAT 49), the EC values for both treatments were lower than those at the fruit stage. Drainage EC values of the control treatment were significantly lower compared to that of the melon cascade treatment during the vegetative stage. As the nutrient solution was continuously reused, it became progressively rich in non-absorbed ions. As a result, during the fruit ripening season (DAT 70–DAT 91), the EC mean values of the cascade drainage were 24% higher than those of the control treatment. However, no statistically significant differences were found.

In Fig. 3, the cumulative volumes of the irrigation and drainage solution (L m^{-2}) of the primary crop, the melon control and cascade treatment, and the cascade system are presented throughout the cultivation period. The total amount of nutrient solution supplied to the primary crop was 331.5 L m^{-2} with a drainage volume of 136.2 L m^{-2} . The irrigation requirements for the melon control and cascade treatment, were 401.6 and 385.8 L m^{-2} respectively, with corresponding total drainage rates of 27% and 25%.

Eq. 1 was used to determine the nutrient solution leaching fraction into the environment of the cascade system. As shown in Fig. 3, the cascade system resulted in a reduction in the leaching fraction, with the drainage volume decreasing to 23.6 L m^{-2} , in contrast to 136.2 L m^{-2} observed in the primary crop. When compared to the cucumber monoculture system, which exhibited a leaching fraction of 40%, the cascade system achieved a significantly lower leaching fraction of 9.6%. Based on these findings, it was determined that a cultivation ratio of 3:1 is required to meet the nutritional demands of one square meter of the melon cascade crop in relation to the primary crop.

Table 1 displays the average concentrations of key macronutrients in the nutrient solution used for irrigation during the primary cultivation, as well as during the vegetative and fruiting stages of the secondary cultivation. As shown in Table 1, significant differences in the average concentrations of most macronutrients were observed at both growth stages. Specifically, in the recycled irrigation nutrient solution used to fertigate the melon cascade treatment, the concentrations of nutrients characterised by high absorption rates from the plants, such as PO_4^{3-} and NH_4^+ , were significantly lower compared to those recorded in the control

Fig. 3. Irrigation and drainage volume (L m^{-2}) of the primary crop, the melon control, and the melon cascade treatments, and the cascade system.

treatment, at both growth stages. Particularly during the fruit stage, the concentrations of NH_4^+ and PO_4^{3-} ions applied in the melon cascade were reduced by 70% and 52%, respectively, compared to the control treatment.

Generally, in the recycled nutrient solution, the concentrations of non-nutrient elements such as Na^+ tend to increase, followed by an increase in those of divalent ions such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and SO_4^{2-} . Consequently, concentrations of these elements were higher in the NS of the melon cascade than those recorded in the control treatment. Potassium (K^+) showed a significant increase during the vegetative stage in the melon cascade treatment which was then reduced during the fruiting period. Moreover, NO_3^- concentrations in the melon cascade treatment were significantly increased throughout the cultivation period, while at the same time exhibited less deviation from the desired value compared to the control treatment.

3.2. Nitrogen and phosphorus leaching into the environment

The cascade system significantly mitigated N and P leaching into the environment (Fig. 4). Compared to other systems and crops, both N and P leaching were significantly lower in the cascade system. In the current study, each system was evaluated independently, and subsequently merged and studied as a cascade system. This cascade system involved utilising the drainage from the cucumber crop for the fertigation of a melon crop, with the cascade treatment of the secondary crop being characterised by the absence of supplementary inputs. Both water and nutrients essential for plant growth were sourced from the pre-existing drainage system of the cucumber crop.

The nitrogen leaching into the environment recorded from the two treatments of the secondary melon crop was 22.38 and 20.97 g N m^{-2} , for the melon control and the cascade treatment, respectively (Fig. 4a). However, the application of the cascade system reduced significantly the N leaching by 75% compared to the monoculture of the melon crop. The monoculture system exhibited higher nitrogen leaching than that of the primary cultivation due to the high amount of N in the standard nutrient solution of the melon crop (18.42 g N m^{-2}).

As depicted in Fig. 4b, the melon control treatment exhibited the highest P leaching (3.14 g P m^{-2}). The substantial decrease in P content in the reused nutrient solution led to a significant reduction in P leaching. Consequently, the melon cascade demonstrated a remarkable 46% decrease in P leaching compared to the melon control treatment. When considering the cascade system as a coupled system, nitrogen losses into the environment were reduced by 75% (5.44 g N m^{-2}) and phosphorus leaching experienced a reduction of 82% compared to the primary crop (2.82 g P m^{-2}).

Fig. 4. (a) Mean nitrogen and (b) phosphorus leaching (g m^{-2}) (\pm S.E.) of the primary crop, the melon control and cascade treatment, and the single and the cascade system. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences between the different treatments. Statistical significance of nitrogen leaching: a: $b^* p \leq 0.05$, a: c, d **** $p \leq 0.001$, a: b * $p \leq 0.05$, a: c, d **** $p \leq 0.001$, b: c ** $p \leq 0.01$, b: d **** $p \leq 0.001$, c: d **** $p \leq 0.001$. Statistical significance of phosphorus leaching: a: b, c, d, e **** $p \leq 0.001$, b: c * $p \leq 0.05$, b: d, e **** $p \leq 0.001$, c: d, e **** $p \leq 0.001$, d, e **** $p \leq 0.001$.

3.3. Plant tissue analysis

Despite the variations in the composition of the irrigation solution between the control and cascade treatments, nutrient concentrations in plant tissues did not present significant differences during the destructive sampling periods (Table 2). In general, the concentration of each element in the plant tissue was proportional to the content found in the nutrient solution. A characteristic example is the concentration of P, which was lower in the tissue of the plants of the cascade treatment compared to that of the control treatment. Nevertheless, no significant differences were noted except in the last destructive sampling, where the P content in the stems of the melon cascade treatment plants, was significantly reduced compared to the control treatment. It is worth noting that the Ca content in the leaves was lower in the melon cascade treatment despite its high concentration in the nutrient solution. This result may be attributed to the antagonistic relationship between Ca and K ions. The K content in the irrigation solution of the melon cascade,

Table 2

Mean nutrient content (N, P, K, Ca and Na expressed in mg g^{-1} of dry matter) (\pm S.E.), in the leaf, stem and fruit tissue of the melon control and melon cascade treatments. Statistical comparisons were conducted for each nutrient element between treatments (control vs. cascade) for the same plant tissue type (leaves, stems and fruit) and sampling date (DAT) and statistically significant differences are indicated by asterisks.

Treatment	DAT	N	P	K	Ca	Na
Leaves						
Control	0	65.45 \pm 2.72	4.92 \pm 0.20	57.06 \pm 0.69	10.10 \pm 0.22	0.84 \pm 0.09
		54.01 \pm 0.64	4.59 \pm 0.27	32.16 \pm 2.42	16.83 \pm 2.19	0.38 \pm 0.04
	30	50.38 \pm 1.36	2.74 \pm 0.11	39.63 \pm 1.54	61.63 \pm 2.76	0.39 \pm 0.02*
		41.34 \pm 0.88	2.01 \pm 0.27	25.26 \pm 1.31	79.16 \pm 4.11	0.45 \pm 0.04
		65.45 \pm 2.72	4.92 \pm 0.20	57.06 \pm 0.69	10.10 \pm 0.22	0.84 \pm 0.09
Cascade	0	55.58 \pm 1.82	3.76 \pm 0.10	35.17 \pm 0.97	16.58 \pm 0.60	0.41 \pm 0.01
		52.22 \pm 1.10	2.90 \pm 0.12	37.51 \pm 1.07	59.95 \pm 2.13	0.49 \pm 0.02
	30	44.66 \pm 2.10	1.52 \pm 0.13	30.39 \pm 2.01	66.29 \pm 2.20**	0.49 \pm 0.06
		47.76 \pm 2.38	6.07 \pm 0.21	72.87 \pm 2.08	1.07 \pm 0.03	1.00 \pm 0.03
		43.60 \pm 3.47	6.78 \pm 0.22	55.97 \pm 2.36	0.67 \pm 0.04	0.48 \pm 0.05
Stems	0	31.07 \pm 0.68	6.35 \pm 0.48	66.48 \pm 2.13	2.64 \pm 0.38*	0.52 \pm 0.04
		30.00 \pm 0.93	4.01 \pm 0.50	54.55 \pm 2.21	9.35 \pm 0.77	0.51 \pm 0.15
	30	47.76 \pm 2.38	6.07 \pm 0.21	72.87 \pm 2.08	1.07 \pm 0.03	1.00 \pm 0.03
		41.60 \pm 0.77	7.11 \pm 0.13	59.88 \pm 2.68	0.59 \pm 1.01	0.47 \pm 0.04
		29.58 \pm 2.85	5.46 \pm 0.41	66.45 \pm 1.37	5.42 \pm 1.01	0.47 \pm 0.04
Fruits	0	28.93 \pm 0.97	3.00 \pm 0.14**	58.01 \pm 1.96	11.08 \pm 0.63	0.60 \pm 0.14
		29.84 \pm 3.47	5.23 \pm 0.48	38.13 \pm 1.46	0.55 \pm 0.10	0.45 \pm 0.01
	30	21.43 \pm 1.94	3.35 \pm 0.45	34.36 \pm 4.78	0.53 \pm 0.88	0.53 \pm 0.06
		27.94 \pm 1.88	4.68 \pm 0.36	37.34 \pm 2.63	0.86 \pm 0.08	0.48 \pm 0.06
		23.48 \pm 3.02	2.11 \pm 0.37	31.26 \pm 4.60	0.41 \pm 0.05	0.55 \pm 0.05

* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$,

** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

during the vegetative period, was supplied to the melon plants in significantly higher concentrations (21.9%) compared to the control melon treatment. However, during the last harvest, the calcium concentration in the leaves of the plants of the melon cascade treatment was significantly reduced by 16%. The low content of calcium in the cascade treatment resulted from its reduced mobility to the fruits, as at DAT 90 the content of calcium in the fruits of the cascade treatment was 22% lower than the control treatment. However, no significant differences were noted. In addition, the Na content in the cascade plant tissues exhibited a modest increase of 8%, despite the elevated concentration of this element in the nutrient solution. Finally, the nitrogen content in all plant parts was similar between treatments. It is worth noting that no nutrient deficiencies were observed in the control and cascade system during the cultivation period.

3.4. Morphological parameters of the secondary crop

Total height and total number of leaves produced by the secondary crop presented on the Table 3. According to the results, both treatments exhibited a similar result in height, whilst the reuse of drainage did not have a significant impact on plant growth. The final mean height for both treatments was recorded on DAT 64 when the melon plants were top cut. The mean plant height was 375.5 and 366.9 cm for the melon control and cascade treatment, respectively.

The total number of leaves produced per plant during the cultivation period of the secondary crop is presented on Table 3. No significant differences were observed during the last measurement as the average number of leaves of the control treatment was similar to that of the cascade treatment. In particular, 53.5 and 50.7 leaves per plant were recorded for the melon control and cascade treatment, respectively.

3.5. Yield

Despite the different fertigation treatments, no significant effect was reported for the total number of fruits produced per m^2 between the treatments of the secondary crop Table 4. The total number of produced fruits per m^2 was 6.4 and 5.8 for the control and the cascade treatment, respectively, while no significant differences were noted between treatments. The average fruit weight was not affected by the different nutrient solution supplied to the plants of the melon cascade t Table 4. The mean fruit weight was similar between treatments, with both the melon control and the cascade treatment resulting in an average fruit weight of 1.53 kg.

As depicted in Fig. 5, the progression of the yield of the secondary crop throughout the cultivation period followed a similar trend for both treatments. The plants of the melon cascade resulted in a slight decrease in production especially evident during the first half of the harvest season (DAT 81), with a notable 30% reduction compared to the control treatment. However, upon completion of the experimental season, the yield of the plants, fertigated with the drainage solution derived from the primary cucumber crop, was similar to those fertigated with a standard nutrient solution, demonstrating no significant differences for the total cultivation period. The harvest began simultaneously for both treatments and extended over 32 days. Throughout the cultivation period, the total average yield of the melon control treatment was 9.9 kg

Table 3

Total plant height (cm), and total number of leaves (\pm S.E.) per plant of the secondary crop. Different letters (a, b) indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments.

	Total Height (cm)	Total number of leaves
Melon control	378.5 \pm 7.2	53.3 \pm 0.9
Melon cascade	366.9 \pm 6.2	50.7 \pm 0.8

No statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found between treatments.

Table 4

Average total number of fruits produced per m^2 and mean fruit weight (kg) (\pm S.E) of the melon control and cascade treatment.

	Total number of fruits produced (fruit m^{-2})	Average fruit weight (kg fruit $^{-1}$)
Melon control	6.4 \pm 0.15	1.53 \pm 0.10
Melon cascade	5.8 \pm 0.32	1.53 \pm 0.12

No statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found between treatments.

Fig. 5. Average cumulative yield (kg m^{-2}) (\pm S.E.) of the melon control and cascade treatment. No statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found between treatments.

m^{-2} , while the yield of the melon cascade treatment was 9.8 kg m^{-2} .

The total fresh and dry weight production observed during the three destructive measurements of the secondary crop are presented in Fig. 6. Up to the 2nd destructive measurement (DAT 60), the fresh weight production of the cascade plants was 8.5 kg m^{-2} closely to the control plants (9.1 kg m^{-2}). The dry weight of the melon control treatment, was increased by 15% compared to the melon cascade treatment. During the last destructive measurement (DAT 90), the fresh weight recorded for the plants of the control treatment of the secondary crop was decreased by 14% compared to that of the control plants. However, the total dry weight produced during the entire cultivation period did not differ between treatments.

3.6. Water use efficiency

Fig. 7 illustrates the water use efficiency of the primary, secondary crop, and both simple and cascade systems. Notable differences were observed between crops and fertigation systems. The primary crop exhibited a WUE of 46.75 kg m^{-3} , which was significantly higher compared to the monoculture melon system and the secondary crop treatments due to high cucumber yield per m^2 (15.5 kg m^{-2}). Due to the utilisation of the primary crop drainages, the WUE of the cascade system experienced a 22.1% increase compared to the cucumber monoculture system, and statistically significant differences were observed between the two tested systems.

The control treatment of the secondary crop exhibited the lowest recorded WUE value among all case scenarios, standing at 24.6 kg m^{-3} . However, when considering the utilisation of drainages from the primary crop to fertigate the secondary (melon cascade) crop as a coupled cascade system, there was a noteworthy 131% increase in WUE compared to monoculture melon crop. Notably, the WUE of the simple system demonstrated a significant 42% reduction compared to the coupled cascade system, emphasising the potential of these systems to

Fig. 6. Mean biomass fresh (a) and dry (b) weight (kg m^{-2}) (\pm S.E) of the melon control and melon cascade treatment. No statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found between treatments.

Fig. 7. Water use efficiency (kg m^{-3}) (\pm S.E) of the primary crop, the melon control and cascade treatment, and the single and cascade system. Statistical significance of a: b, c, d **** $p \leq 0.001$, b: c, d **** $p \leq 0.001$, c: d * $p \leq 0.05$.

enhance water use efficiency in cultivations.

3.7. N, p and k use efficiency

The NUE, PUE and KUE were evaluated for the primary, secondary cultivation, as well as the simple and cascade cultivation systems (Fig. 8). The application of the cascade hydroponic system significantly increased the NUE and PUE compared to the cucumber monoculture system by 21.7% and 21.8%, respectively. More specifically, the primary crop exhibited a NUE of 339.7 kg N^{-1} and a PUE of 575.2 kg P^{-1} . The high NUE and PUE values were attributed to the primary crop, primarily affected by its high yield (15.5 kg m^{-2}). Compared to the melon monoculture system, the NUE and PUE of the cascade hydroponic system were significantly increased by 146.5% and 211.4%, respectively.

Both melon cultivation treatments (control, cascade) displayed the lowest NUE values, significantly lower compared to the other systems. Similarly, the melon control treatment recorded the lowest PUE, significantly reduced compared to the melon cascade treatment and the other systems. The recycled nutrient solution used to fertigate the plants in the melon cascade treatment was characterised by low phosphorus content. As a result, the melon cascade treatment demonstrated a notable 60% increase in PUE compared to that of the control treatment. Moreover, the application of the cascade system significantly increase in

PUE (by 44.8%) compared to the simple system.

The KUE was not affected with the implementation of the cascade system. This can be attributed to the low potassium content in the reused nutrient solution, resulting in a 9% increase in KUE of the melon cascade treatment compared to the primary crop. Additionally, the cascade system enhanced potassium use efficiency by 22% compared to melon monoculture. Notably, significant differences were observed between the cascade system and both the secondary cultivation control and the monoculture system, with variances of 27% and 23% respectively.

4. Discussion

The appropriate combination of primary and secondary crops constitutes a crucial factor for the successful implementation of a cascade hydroponic system. In this study, a cascade hydroponic system was evaluated in comparison to monoculture systems. The recycling of drainage nutrient solution leads to an incremental accumulation of salts. For this reason, the secondary crop should be more salt-tolerant than the primary one. Furthermore, the nutritional requirements of both crops should align to optimise the synergistic functioning of the cascade hydroponic system.

4.1. Evaluation of the recycled nutrient solution

Melon is considered a crop with moderate salt tolerance and less sensitivity compared to cucumber (Bar-Yossef, 2008). According to Colla et al., (2006), EC values higher than 3.2 dS m^{-1} in the root environment can decrease the yield of the melon plants. In the current study, the average EC of the reused nutrient solution (2.67 dS m^{-1}) was similar to the average EC of the standard irrigation solution used for the control treatment (2.5 dS m^{-1}), with no impact on production. Grieve et al., (2012) reported an 8.4% decrease in melon plant production for each unit increase in electrical conductivity. As the nutrient solution reused, its composition and macronutrient ratios undergo alteration (Neocleous and Savvas, 2015). Zhang et al., (2006) used a hydroponic waste solution on a musk melon crop. They observed, that the composition of the reused nutrient solution was richer in cations such as Ca^{2+} and K^{+} , while anions (excluding nitrate ions), and were present in lower concentrations. In this work, the composition of the reused nutrient solution demonstrated a significant excess in NO_3^- , Ca^{2+} , and Na^{+} ions, while the K^{+} concentration was higher only during the vegetative period. The easily absorbed ions (PO_4^{3-} and NH_4^+) content in the reused nutrient solution as expected was significantly lower than the standard nutrient solution throughout the cultivation period. Despite the different composition of the recycled solution, the performance of the secondary

Fig. 8. NUE (kg N⁻¹) (a), PUE (kg P⁻¹) (b) and KUE (kg K⁻¹) (c) (\pm S.E) of the primary crop, the control and cascade treatment, the single and cascade system. Different letters indicate the statistically significant differences. *Statistical significance of NUE:* a: b, c, d **** $p \leq 0.0001$, b: c ** $p \leq 0.01$, b: d **** $p \leq 0.0001$, c: d **** $p \leq 0.0001$, *Statistical significance of PUE:* a: b *** $p \leq 0.001$, a: c, d **** $p \leq 0.0001$, b: c, d **** $p \leq 0.0001$, c: d **** $p \leq 0.0001$, *Statistical significance of KUE:* a: b * $p \leq 0.05$.

cultivation was not affected. The aforementioned results are in agreement with those of [Neocleous and Savvas \(2015\)](#) where they concluded that increasing the EC with the aim of sustaining the K:Ca:Mg ratio in the nutrient solution has a greater negative impact on production compared to maintaining the predetermined EC. [Cabello et al., \(2009\)](#) did not observe a significant reduction in melon productivity when applying deficient nitrogen fertilisation. Similarly, [Demiral and Koseoglu \(2005\)](#) did not find a significant reduction in production when applying different amounts of potassium. However, they observed that the optimum application of potassium increased the number of marketable fruits. The aforementioned results underscore that the cascade cropping systems can be optimized by finding species whose performance is not negatively affected by nutrient solutions with modified ionic compositions. Moreover, our findings, also suggest that the melon crop can be cultivated hydroponically with PO_4^{3-} and NH_4^+ concentrations much lower than those recommended from [Sonneveld and Voogt \(2009\)](#).

4.2. Concentration of the main macronutrients in the plant tissue of the secondary crop

In general, despite the different composition of the irrigation nutrient solution, there were no differences in plant tissue analysis except from P and Ca. The lower phosphate and ammonium content in the recycled nutrient solution resulted in lower P content in the stem tissue during the last measurement. According to [Ben and Kafkafi \(2007\)](#), the stem is used as a storage site for P, which is subsequently transported to the leaves. The stored phosphorus aids in the transfer of sugars to the fruits during the fruiting period. In the current research,

despite the high concentration of Ca and Na in the recycled nutrient solution, the concentration of Ca in the leaves was significantly reduced during the last destructive measurement, while the concentration of Na did not differ in plant tissues between the treatments. This is in contrast with the findings of [Feigin \(1990\)](#), who observed that in hydroponic melon cultivation, supplying 10% -15% of the total nitrogen as ammonium increased the Na content in plant tissue while decreased the Ca content.

4.3. Morphological parameters and plant growth response of the secondary crop

The reuse of the drainage solution did not affect the growth and development of the secondary crop. Nevertheless, in a study conducted by [Castellanos et al., \(2011\)](#), on a melon crop, the application of low nitrogen amounts did not negatively affect fruit production, while the excessive nitrogen application led to excessive vegetative growth. Furthermore, they observed that the optimal application of PO_4^{3-} and NH_4^+ , contributed significantly to the earlier production. Similar results were also observed in the present study, as the plants irrigated with the standard nutrient solution yielded the majority of the production earlier, compared to the melon cascade treatment where the levels of PO_4^{3-} and NH_4^+ were significantly lower during the cultivation period. However, the total yield of the cascade plants was not affected by the deficit supply of the aforementioned ions. This response is in line with those of [Nerson et al. \(1987\)](#), who highlighted that the melon plants were more sensitive to nitrogen than to phosphorus deficit supply.

4.4. Cultivation ratio and water leaching of the cascade system

In addition to the technical difficulties discussed in the introduction, the design of an efficient cascade hydroponic system requires precise dimensioning of both donor and receiver crop areas (Puccinelli et al., 2023b). This dimensioning can be based on either the crop water needs or their nutritional requirements (García-Caparrós et al., 2018b; Ruff-Salís et al., 2020). García-Caparrós et al., (2018a) introduced a model for calculating the optimal cascade system size, incorporating both crop water uptake and the leaching fraction, depending on water salinity (Massa et al., 2020). In this study, the ratio between the primary and secondary crop, tailored to the irrigation needs per square meter of the primary and the secondary crop, resulting a 3:1 (m²) primary-secondary crop cultivation ratio. Elvanidi et al., (2020), used diluted cucumber drainage to meet the needs of rosemary, basil, and mint, with ratios of 1:1 to 1:1.5. In a cascade system, leafy vegetables were irrigated with tomato drainage at ratios of 1:1 to 1:3 (Karatsivou et al., 2023), reducing the leaching fraction by 90%. In the present study, the dimensioning of the cascade system reduces by 75% the nutrient solution leaching into the environment (9%), compared to the initial drainage volume of the primary crop (40%). The precise design of a cascade system is crucial for maximizing the resources efficiency while minimizing water and nutrient leaching.

4.5. Nitrogen and phosphorus leaching into the environment

The reuse of a drainage solution to fertigate a secondary or even tertiary cultivations has the potential to result in a substantial depletion of nitrate and phosphate ions from the nutrient solution in the drainage. These ions are the primary source of pollution of the groundwater (Muñoz et al., (2008); Massa et al., 2020). In this study, the cascade system reduced the nitrogen and phosphorus leaching by 70% and 86%, respectively, due to the absorption of water and nutrients by the secondary crop. Incorcci et al., (2003) found that recycling the nutrient solution from a semi-closed system of table tomatoes to cherry tomatoes grown in NFT did not significantly reduce the yield, while simultaneously achieving a noteworthy 65% reduction in pollutant nutrient leaching. Similarly, Muñoz et al. (2012), reduced the N leachate and the environmental impact of the climate change category by 60 and 21%, respectively, when applying the drainage nutrient solution from a hydroponic tomato to a soil-grown cherry tomato, while the eutrophication category increased by 10% due to productivity reduction. The study and the implementation of systems that reduce the impact of agriculture on the environment is of high importance for the sustainability of intensive greenhouse production.

4.6. Water, n and p and k use efficiency of the cascade system

Cascade hydroponic systems have the potential to maximise water and nutrients use efficiency compared to open soilless monoculture systems, when the drainage from the primary crop, is fully recycled. In our study, the combination of the cucumber a melon crop in a cascade system, proved to be an efficient resource use system. The WUE and NUE demonstrated an increase by 21.7% and 21.8% respectively, compared to the monoculture of the cucumber crop. In a similar study involving leafy vegetables as secondary crop, the cascade system improved the WUE 14 to 30% and also increased the NUE and PUE (Karatsivou et al., 2023). Potassium use efficiency of the primary crop, did not differ from that of the melon control and the melon cascade treatments, due to high total amounts of potassium used in the primary crop. However, the cascade system increased the KUE by 9% and 27% compared to the primary and secondary crop control treatment, respectively, emphasising the system's ability to enhance nutrient effectiveness regardless of whether they are utilised in small or large quantities.

Improving WUE is essential for greenhouse production systems (Damerum et al., 2021). The recycling of the nutrient solution within a

system leads to increased WUE. Finding alternative species that perform well as secondary crops is essential for expanding the application of cascade cropping systems, where secondary crops are often characterized by low productivity (Massa et al., 2020)

5. Conclusion

The application of a cascade hydroponic system has the main advantages of water and nutrient saving, while the discharge of pollutants such as nitrates and phosphates is reduced. Moreover, the reuse of the drainage nutrient solution in these systems, resulted in an increase in water and nutrients efficiency. According to the findings of this study, the melon crop can be grown hydroponically as a secondary crop in a cascade system, using as a nutrient solution the drainages derived from a hydroponic cucumber crop, without any yield reduction. Cascade cropping systems provide the opportunity, even for low-tech infrastructures, to mitigate water and nutrient runoff, while simultaneously minimising inputs of resources. The evaluation of the above results and their comparison with the international literature indicate that cascade cropping systems represent a significant step toward the sustainability of greenhouse cultivation. The implementation of the cascade systems introduces novel prospects for crop production enabling the achievement of high productivity with low resource inputs. Further research is required to assess productive combinations with different plant species as secondary crops, thereby reducing the knowledge gap regarding plant response and productivity within a cascade system.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ioannis Naounoulis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Sofia Faliagka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Efi Levizou:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Nikolaos Katsoulas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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